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D4.1.1 - Whitepaper on DaMSym

Reasoning and first exploitation of DaMSym Platform

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Document Overview

Scope

The global purpose of WP₄ is the semantic analysis of key terms found in our case study, namely the text of the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed in its various translations. The ITSERR project envisions that advanced knowledge for the history of religious studies will emerge from these studies, but also that new computer tools will be made available to fellow scholars for extracting information from the ancient texts under consideration. Language models, particularly those based on Large Language Models (LLM), can be used to analyze the text of the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed in order to identify significant semantic patterns. These models will be optimized (e.g., fine-tuning operation) over a wide range of Christian texts for the different translation languages under consideration. To analyze the text of the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed for the purpose of identifying significant semantic patterns, rule-based or probabilistic architecture tools can be used. In particular, Large Language Models (LLMs) may eventually be finetuned to perform a wide range of semantic operations on the Christian texts for the various translation languages under consideration whose amount of data currently available allows it. With these models it will be possible to obtain advanced semantic representations to facilitate the identification of relationships, similarities and deep meanings for key terms in the Creed. Data mining will then be applied to this enriched corpus to extract detailed information about semantic relationships within the Creed, helping us to better understand the theological and historical significance of each term in the various translations and interpretations of the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed.

The Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed is a formula that states the core principles of the Christian faith. Its development began from the first formulaic homologies of the New Testament, passed through liturgical-baptismal, catechetical and apologetical steps to finally come to be written in the Council of Nicaea and of Council of Constantinople. Nevertheless, first attestation of this Creed is stated by the Council of Chalcedon 451 and from then on, the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed became a core textual resource for the Christian traditions and was translated in almost every language the Christians belonged to. The Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed was initially written in Ancient Greek while its translation into Latin appeared very soon during the V century.

Gezen in the book "Istoria slavianskova perevoda Simvol veri", published in 1884 (second edition: 2015) notes that the Slavic translation of the Creed was made even before St. Cyril and Methodius, although this translation could receive its final edition only after the invention of the Slavic alphabet. Since the 9th century in the Eastern Church, when performing the Sacraments, the Symbol of the 2nd Ecumenical Council of Constantinople was already used.

For the Sanskrit language, a translation of the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed into Sanskrit by the Anglican Reverend William Hodge Mill, made in 1823: the printed text in Devanāgarī characters was transliterated and it will be therefore analyzed in this shape here.

In the Christian and Muslim Arab context, the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed is preserved in many texts that differ according to the confession of the author of the work or its translator. Muslim authors largely use the version of the Nestorian al-Tabari (9th century), a Christian author who converted to Islam; instead, Christian authors who write in Arabic do not rely on a single formula. The question remains open as to whether the oldest author drew on the liturgical Syriac formula or made use of an ancient Arabic translation, not yet identified.

Objectives

Deliverable 4.1.1 in its original form had a deadline set for the 1st September 2024 and was written in the following format:

This whitepaper describes the reasoning and possible exploitation of DaMSym, intended as a software that performs several functions: 1) word embedding extraction 2) machine translation 3) text classification and document understanding 4) standoff properties annotation 5) properties visualization. Each function is detailed separately, but the whitepaper also describes DaMSym in its entirety, as a single platform for performing all the above tasks in subsequent phases

In any case, from the initial draft of this deliverable to the present, the comprehension of the project around DaMSym is progressed and we convened to intervene slightly modifying this description in order to align it to the state of the art in the field of NLP for ancient languages, to make it more detailed and corresponding to the direction we are following in the scholar and developing process. This update intervention has been applied also to the other 4 deliverables of WP4 that now reflect the nature of our work in a more informative way. Therefore, the deliverable 4.1.1. has not been submitted by the 1st September 2024 but by November the 7th of this year. Deliverable 4.1.1. appears now in this shape:

This whitepaper describes the reasoning and possible exploitation of DaMSym, intended as a software platform that performs several functions on ancient text corpora specifically prepared: 1) setup of the various corpora for the WP4 studied languages 2) PoS tagging techniques 3) word embedding extraction 4) document understanding through comparison with corpora 5) properties visualization. Each function is detailed separately, but the whitepaper also describes DaMSym in its entirety, as a single platform for performing all the above tasks in subsequent phases.

Here is detailed how we understand and pursue the various points numbered in the updated deliverable 4.1.1:

- Every survey on ancient texts is pursued by interrogating a corpus, which is the digital library containing textual material. For this reason, it's important to detail the work which has been done and is meant to be prosecuted around the construction of ancient language corpora or in order to collect raw textual material from the most up-dated sources to construct state-of-the-art linguistic datasets;
- Related to, but not coincident with the corpus topic, we'll have to give account also of the Part of Speech (PoS) tagging techniques used in the annotating process. It should be considered that in Natural Language Processing (NLP) applied to ancient texts, PoS gains a wider meaning compared to the simple description of the role of the target term: PoS ends up grouping all the grammatical, morphological and syntactical analysis applied to the text and summarized into the tags annotated to the same text. To name the most well-known: tokenization, multi-word token expansion, lemmatization, morphological parsing, dependency parsing, named-entity recognition (NER). PoS tagging is usually accomplished using dedicated tools that can be either rule-based or trained on a stochastic workflow. In any case, they integrate the text expliciting information from the function of a term (which one holds and which is held) to the syntactical relations in the phrase, passing through grammar

and morphology. It depends on one or more tools to express information hidden in the text that are then usually visualized in treebanks. All these instruments help the scholar to set the corpus for further exploration;

- With “word embedding” we point towards a technique in NLP where words are transformed into numerical vectors that capture features according to their meaning, be it grammatical, morphological or semantic relationships between words based on their context in a corpus. With “embedding” we refer to the numeric transformation offered by an encoder working on a certain amount of tokens. The text is transformed into the form of multi-dimensional vectors (usually, dimensions in the order of hundreds) by the encoder: this kind of tool is nowadays usually based on a Transformer architecture (self-attention technology) that provide the model the capacity to stress the focus on more important tokens compared to others. Encoders provide vectors that can be further exploited in subsequent passages or tasks based on the distance of a word or a sentence to another in a multi-dimensional space;
- With “document understanding through comparison with corpora” we refer to the processes of automatically assigning predefined categories or labels to text documents, helping in organizing, filtering, or summarizing textual information for better comprehension. We understand this broadly: understanding a word through its comparison to the corpus, encoding words and sentences, comparing them to the encoded corpus, understanding and labeling literary genres to a target text after resuming it, locating it in a more probable period and classify it according to author, area or other categories. These goals are usually achieved by generative models, the most well-known, nowadays, is GPT but ancient and relatively vocabulary poor languages lack the possibility to construct effectively a transformer model. Therefore, we consider setting new state-of-the-art strategies in order to achieve these goals in new ways;
- “Properties visualization” in NLP refers to techniques used to graphically represent various attributes, patterns, and characteristics of textual data or model outputs to gain insights, understand relationships, or debug NLP models. It helps researchers and practitioners to better understand how textual data or a model behaves. In NLP, visualization techniques include word clouds and heatmaps for word frequency, t-SNE for embedding projections, and attention heatmaps for understanding Transformer models. Dependency trees and topic modeling graphs help explore syntax, entities, and topics. Model performance is visualized using confusion matrices, ROC curves, and sentiment distribution charts.

Structure

This deliverable is structured according to these five points and for each point we discuss the proceedings of the ancient languages in WP4 following this order: Latin, Ancient Greek, Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic, Sanskrit and Arabic. With regard to the languages investigated by DamSym, we are proceeding on the basis of the expertise of the researchers and PhD students officially involved in the WP as a result of the call for applications published in relation to WP4. Consequently, during the project's duration, we cannot introduce the study of other Late Antiquity and Medieval languages relevant to the history of Christianity. However, the hope is to do so in the near future, as well as to expand the scope of DaMSym to include the analysis of additional texts beyond the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed.

Team

The WP Leader is Professor Fabrizio D’Avenia (University of Palermo - UniPa), while Costanza Bianchi (University of Modena and Reggio Emilia - UniMoRE) and Marianna Napolitano (University of Modena and Reggio Emilia - UniMoRE) are the Product owners. The team directly involves 4 Phd Candidates: Federico Iezzi (University of Modena and Reggio Emilia - UniMoRE), Elia Scapini (University of Modena and Reggio Emilia - UniMoRE), Usman Nawaz (University of Palermo - UniPa) and Irfan Ali (University of Palermo - UniPa). Ivana Panzeca (University of Palermo - UniPa) and Igor Spanò (University of Palermo - UniPa) are the junior assistant professors (RTD-A) included in our work package.

Marianna NAPOLITANO	UniMoRE	Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic
Usman NAWAZ	UniPa – Liliana LO PRESTI	Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic
Ivana PANZECA	UniPa	Arabic
Giovanni PUCCETTI	CNR	Arabic
Igor SPANÒ	UniPa	Sanskrit
Irfan ALÌ	UniPa – Marco LA CASCIA	Sanskrit
Federico IEZZI	UniMoRE	Latin and Greek
Elia SCAPINI	UniMoRE	Latin and Greek
Marcella CORNIA	UniMoRE (WP6)	Latin and Greek
Costanza BIANCHI	UniMoRE	Coptic
Fabio QUATTRINI	UniMoRE - Silvia CASCIANELLI	Coptic
Lorenzo BIANCHI	CNR - Fabrizio SEBASTIANI	Coptic

As of Oct. 29, the team expanded for the Slavic section with the participation of the CNR, represented by Maria Cassese and Fabrizio Sebastiani. Activities for Latin and Greek languages are fully covered by WP6, while humanities research for Slavonic is supported by WP3 (Criterion). Regarding Coptic, due to the scarcity of data, the work is covered in a partial way and is supervised by an assignee from the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia. In fact, Coptic not just is poorly attested, it is also scarcely digitized. Therefore the team working on this topic has decided to focus firstly on Handwritten Text Recognition in order to overcome this issue.

1. Setup of the various corpora for the WP4 studied languages

Latin

Every NLP technique is to be applied to a certain amount of text which is technically addressed as a “corpus”. The Latin corpus we decided to work with is based on [Corpus Corporum](#). This project, in continuous development at the University of Zurich under the direction of Philipp Roelli, Institute for Greek and Latin Philology, uses exclusively free and open software and is non-commercial. Furthermore, it happens to provide meta-data, including periods and authors, making it suitable for WP4-Latin projects, even though metadata is not uniformly present in all cases anyway. At first, we tried to include in our Latin corpus also data collected from [100CC](#). This project saves Latin text scraping the internet, which comports a few downsides: meta-data is lacking and the text tends to be dirty, including, especially, “lorem ipsum” material. Even if there’s a 100CC Latin corpus emendate from “Lorem Ipsum” on HuggingFace, still the corpus is not surfable through date or author. For this reason we decided to stick to Corpus Corporum.

Fig. 1: Screenshot of CorpusCorporum webpage

Ancient Greek

The most complete corpus for Ancient Greek text is the Thesaurus Linguae Graecae (TLG). It is a digital collection of Greek literature from antiquity to the present era. The research program was founded in 1972, is based at the University of California, Irvine, and is nowadays directed by Professor Maria Pantelia. TLG allows users to navigate texts by several search features (author, date, location, genre, etc.), to inquire the corpus through state-of-the-art tools (e.g. n-grams), to visualize textual statistics, and to dynamically call vocabulary tools on the target words. An abridged version is publicly available but to unlock all the features of the TLG, a subscription is required, this is not open data. For that reason, digital humanists dedicated to the NLP for Ancient Greek tend to prefer open access databases, even if they contain much less texts than TLG. Among them one can count the [PROIEL treebank](#), [Diorisis Corpus](#) (Vatri and McGillivray 2018), [Perseus Digital Library](#), and [First1KGreek](#). We also noticed the large corpus created and published in [Riemenschneider and Frank \(2023\)](#) that produced a much larger corpus of Greek text (100+ million words) using additional sources but we’re still in evaluation.

With them, it has recently been created the [GLAUx corpus](#), the largest Ancient Greek open data corpus available up to these days. GLAUx is a large corpus (currently 20M tokens) of Ancient Greek (8th century BC - roughly 4th century AD), automatically annotated for morphology and syntax and

has been worked on by Alek Keersmaekers and other scholars. We plan to adopt this source to achieve tasks numbered in deliverable 3. GLAUx, in any case, will require to be sided with other sources because it lacks the golden patristic century (IV century) and later centuries. Federico Iezzi and Elia Scapini have developed a tool which can download, incorporate and preprocess all the textual material from GLAUx extracting a unique .txt file cleaned from unnecessary diacritics signs and where splitted words (e.g. end of line) are reconstructed correctly. We also plan to implement a navigation system that allows us to select the training material for Ancient Greek BERT (see below chapter three) automatically by year, genre or author.

Besides GLAUx, and in order to test a new retrieval technique, which is going to be explained later in this document, we needed another case-study corpus corresponding to certain prerequisites. Eustathius of Antioch's collection of fragments (CCSG 2002) seemed to suit promisingly since it can be read and controlled in the time of a Ph.D. 3 years program and contains the target expressions meant to be retrieved. We have already created a small test corpus and we program to collect all the fragments from Eustathius by the next deliverable report. We plan to apply PoS tagging to this corpus testing first [the tool released with Ancient-Greek-BERT](#) which has an accuracy of ~90 percent on the 3 treebanks available at the moment of its creation, in 2021.

Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic

The computational study of Old Church Slavonic (OCS - attested from the late 9th to the 11th centuries) and Church Slavonic texts poses special problems. This is a scarce resource, and developing a comprehensive corpus that can support linguistic analysis will require some complicated processes. As researchers interested in computation analysis in the domain of ancient languages, we faced a double challenge, not only is the language in itself complex, but the data is scattered and sparse, distributed among several archives and resources.

Our current research aimed to fill this gap by actively collecting, and curating the Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic manuscripts, especially religious texts, which form the bulk of the surviving corpus. Locating, standardizing, and preparing for computational use of these materials requires significant effort.

The corpus we have so far compiled forms a critical foundation effort for linguistic analysis, however, we are always seeking new sources of texts which we can add to the expanding corpus.

In the following, we report the various steps needed to collect the dataset.

Data Gathering Phase

Initial data acquisition was done from various online repositories. Since this required the use of web scraping, several data extraction methodologies were undertaken using Python scripts. Data was typically obtained either in HTML format or plain text format. In those repositories where direct extraction methods were not allowed, the files were downloaded in PDF format. These are of different natures, including HTML, plain text, and PDFs, which presented some challenges. Because of the different structures, they needed extra preprocessing steps to put them in a uniform format for further computational analysis.

It follows that the first stage of the work has been dedicated to the collection of texts from several corpora available online in open access.

Until this moment our corpus is made of the texts taken from the following projects:

1. [Cyrillomethodiana](#): a web portal that gives information about a series of projects under which the Histdict system was created and about other projects that used the available digital tools. The Histdict system does not include only the corpus and OCS dictionaries but also digital tools for processing Slavic Medieval texts and amongst them there is a semi-automatic rule-based PoS recognition tool linked to the grammatical dictionary of OCS. The PoS recognition tool allows to use the virtual keyboard (kbd) for entering the wordform to be analyzed. The PoS tool does not only show the lemma and the grammatical features of the analyzed wordform but displays also the whole inflectional paradigm in all its orthographic varieties – Bulgarian, Russian and Serbian. In the field of a collaboration with the University of Sofia St. Kliment Ohridski, which is the institution responsible for the contents of the web portal, we have access to texts of this corpus in xml format.

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2. [Syntacticus](#): an umbrella project for the *PROIEL Treebank*, the *Tromsø Old Russian and OCS Treebank* (TOROT) and the *Information Structure and Word Order Change in Germanic and Romance Languages* (ISWOC) *Treebank*, which all use the same annotation system and share similar linguistic priorities. The *Syntacticus* provides easy access to around a million morphosyntactically annotated tokens from 10 early Indo-European languages. The amount of available token is 140276 for Old Church Slavonic and 235,275 for Old Russian.
3. [Library of sacred literature Orthodox Gymnasium in the name of St. Sergius of Radonezh](#); an electronic library dedicated to Christian patristic literature. As an open-access digital library, [orthlib.ru](#) provides readers with an extensive collection of written works that are considered to be some of the most significant in Christian theological thought. It aims to deliver these texts to a wide audience and is specifically tailored to Russian speaking readers. The library features patristic texts from influential figures such as Clement of Rome, Polycarp of Smyrna, Melito of Sardis, Irenaeus of Lyons, Athanasius the Great, Cyril of Jerusalem, Basil the Great, John Chrysostom, John Damascene, Gregory Palamas, and many others. Primary goal of this open access library is to increase the availability of patristic texts to the readers, with all the texts available in modern spelling for easy reading. Liturgical texts in Church Slavonic are included. However, till now, we have been able to use only texts in pdf format and not texts that are in HIP format.
4. [Orthodoxy and the World](#): the largest library of holy theological literature and books by modern theologians. This library uses materials from the *Publishing House of the Sisterhood of St. Ignatius of Stavropol*; from the online libraries [Orthodox Encyclopedia](#) [Church Research Center](#), [Pravoslavnaja Beseda](#), [Library of sacred literature Orthodox](#)

[Gymnasium in the name of St. Sergius of Radonezh](#) and other open resources. Books in Church Slavonic are available in the following formats: pdf; epub; fb2; mobi.

5. [St. Petersburg Corpus Of Hagiographic Texts \(SKAT\)](#): an electronic corpus of Old Russian hagiographic literature, created at the *Department of Mathematical Linguistics, Faculty of Philology, St. Petersburg State University*. As reported in the web site of the corpus, Russian hagiographic literature of the XV-XVII centuries is characterized by exceptional richness. It was at this time and in this genre that phraseology, standard verbal complexes were formed, which word masters creatively used in texts built according to certain laws of the genre. The language of hagiographic works largely determined the fate and character of the Russian literary language of this time. The reflection of this language is the primary task of the created corpus of texts of Russian hagiographies of the XV-XVII centuries, which is achieved in particular through a wide geographical coverage of different territories. Texts are available in xml and pdf formats.

6. In addition other texts are taken from a) [obdurodon.org](#) which is the development platform for David J. Birnbaum's digital humanities projects; b) [Thesaurus Indogermanischer Text- und Sprachmaterialien \(TITUS\)](#), whose primary aim is the coordinated recording of the relevant original texts of ancient Indo-European languages. The idea of "entrusting" such texts to the new electronic medium, which was rather difficult to establish at the time, was not really new, indeed TITUS draws inspiration from the *Thesaurus Linguae Graecae* project mentioned above.

An integrated dataset is still under development therefore, at this stage of the work we do not have exact information regarding the total amount of tokens available. However the lack of a single comprehensive and large dataset has two clear consequences: 1) texts included in the dataset we are developing covers a large periodization (XI-XVIII century): this means also a lack in the standardization of the characters and of the orthographic signs; 2) texts are available in different formats, it follows that a preliminary work would be needed in order to make all of them available in a standard and unique format.

To this should be added that in order to enlarge the available corpus, some tests have been conducted with some tools for OCR and HTR. In particular some tests have been conducted with the book scanner Treventus in order to enlarge the corpus with texts contained in critical editions of Slavic manuscripts – here is important to consider that also this field of research needs to be improved and enlarged, however some critical editions are available at the Dossetti library in Bologna and some others have been consulted at the *Centre for Slavo-Byzantine Studies "Prof. Ivan Dujčev"* in Sofia. However the scanner Treventus does not have Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic among the available characters and this makes it very difficult to use the texts after they have been scanned.

Additional tests have been conducted with the tools E-scriptorium and Transkribus but unfortunately in both cases results have not been good enough to allow the use of these tools in order to proceed to the required enlargement of the corpus. Below, is possible finding an example of the result for manuscripts of different periods. Results from E-Scriptorium showed to be a little more encouraging than the ones of Transkribus. However, although the preliminary work of editing of the text by applying the segmentation through the regions and line mode, results show that with the available models a long training would be need in order to advance the improvement curve and at this stage

this kind of work cannot be conducted considered the limited number of human resources involved in the project and considered the limited number of available critical editions of Slavic manuscripts and of course the limited period of the project. Also in the field of a collaboration with some colleagues of the University of Freiburg, this task will be developed hopefully in a future project.

Below are images which show that although some words and phrases are not recognized, part of the text is read correctly. However in almost all the words some characters need to be corrected.

Fig. 2: Сборник на йеросхимонах Спиридон началото на XIX в. [Ръкопис] . лист 23 - грѣб
(Citation link: <http://unilib-dspace.nasledstvo.bg/xmlui/handle/nls/1488>)

Fig. 3: Электронный каталог (Электронная библиотека рукописей). F.I.37 Евангелие тетр. 1551 г. - л. 331 об. – 332.

Fig. 3: Электронный каталог (Электронная библиотека рукописей). F.I.376 Сборник. 1348 г. - л. III об. - 1

Fig. 4: Сборник на ѱеросхимонах Спиридон началото на XIX в. [Рѣкопис] . лист 23 - грѣб
(Citation link: <http://unilib-dspace.nasledstvo.bg/xmlui/handle/nls/1488>)

Fig. 5: Электронный каталог (Электронная библиотека рукописей). F.I.376 Сборник. 1348 г. - л. III об. - 1

Fig. 6: Электронный каталог (Электронная библиотека рукописей). F.I.37 Евангелие тетр. 1551 г. - л. 331 об. – 332.

appeared correctly on the original websites (compare Fig. 7, Fig. 8). From this, we understand that the source of the problem is to be found in the use of Persona User Area (PUA) [7] or unregistered Unicode codepoints in the original text.

Fig. 9: Oxygen Xml Editor for TEI. As shown in the image, some characters are not readable due to encoding issues.

a. Challenges in Character Recognition

This is why the research conducted by the doctoral student enrolled at the University of Palermo focused on addressing this issue, which does not concern only the Cyrillomethodiana texts but is a common problem in all the other texts considered for the development of our dataset. Despite the collaboration with Sofia University—thanks to which we were able to obtain fonts for reading these texts in the early months of the ITSERR project—the decision was made to develop a converter capable of recognizing Cyrillomethodiana characters by matching them with their existing Unicode equivalents. The idea behind this initiative was to create a precise conversion tool that would align these letters with those recognized by most open-access Slavic language fonts. In the future, this conversion tool is also intended to be integrated into the lemmatization tool.

```
replacements = {  
    '✉': 'H',  
    '<': '^',  
    '■': 'y',  
    '↻': 'I-E',  
    '◀': 'H',  
}
```

Fig. 10: Specific Characters and output problem

b. Tools and Methodologies

Several Python libraries and platforms were tested during this research, including:

- ❖ **NLTK, Spacy, TextBlob, BeautifulSoup, and CLTK:** Used for web scraping, text extraction, and natural language processing.
- ❖ **Compilers such as PyCharm, Google Colab, and Jupyter:** Used for code execution and debugging. However, across all platforms, the issue of compromised characters persisted.
- ❖ **Oxygen XML Editor:** This has been utilized to process the TEI-encoded files, which has revealed further character integrity problems. Using these utilities, partial analysis of the data was possible, but most of the characters extracted were corrupted, preventing comprehensive linguistic analysis.

c. Problem Analysis and proposed solutions

One of the major hurdles is the use of unregistered Unicode codepoints by the data owners via PUA to encode some Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic characters. Such non-standard characters cannot be accurately processed or searched with conventional methods. This results in the corruption of the text when extracting the data.

To address these issues, we contacted the data owners to request access to the text in the original format or details on the proper Unicode codepoints for Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic characters. Since we were not able to establish such a contact we performed the following steps:

- ❖ **Data Normalization via Mapping:** Design a mapping table that would translate the PUA characters into their proper Unicode character counterparts. From this mapping, a Python program could be written to undertake such a transformation process for uniformity of the text in a single machine-readable format. Fig. 10 shows the Python dictionary used to perform the mapping. Thus, we applied it in order to open the door for further processing. Further details are provided in the next sub-section.

- ❖ **Alternative Text Sources:** Look for other sources of Old Church Slavonic texts where such limiting encoding practices are not in use.

The research highlights the technical challenges associated with web scraping Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic texts, particularly the use of PUA encoding. While partial solutions such as data normalization and communication with data owners may offer a path forward, the broader issue of data accessibility and standardization must be addressed.

We proposed and implemented a remapping solution for PUA but it is also very interesting to know that there are still some characters that need some kind of special intention because we were facing some difficulties in adjusting them even in remapping. We can discuss Titlo (an extended diacritic symbol initially used in early Cyrillic and Glagolitic manuscripts, e.g., in Old Church Slavonic and Old East Slavic languages) to understand the depth of the hurdle that we are facing for some characters.

The issue presented in the document revolves around the incorrect visualization and rendering of the "COMBINING CYRILLIC TITLO" character (Unicode: U+0483) in various fonts used for Old Church Slavonic texts. The main concern is that this character appears incorrectly on top of the previous character rather than the following one, leading to possible semantic errors in the rendered text, particularly when using certain Unicode fonts, Slavonic Computing Initiative [8] fonts such as MenaionUnicode and other fonts tested for compatibility, as listed below:

- MonomakhUnicode
- FiraSlav
- Shafarik
- VertogradUnicode
- CathismaUnicode
- OglavieUnicode
- PomorskyUnicode

During our tests, each font introduced its own issues, such as rendering boxes or failing to position U+0483 properly, despite some fonts handling other characters correctly. For instance,

- ❖ **Text Rendering Issues:** In Python, using Pycharm for Unicode text, the combining character U+0483 did not appear in the intended position. When transferring the same text to LibreOffice for PDF generation, it altered the font and rendered U+0483 incorrectly for the entire text.
- ❖ **Consistency with Other Sources:** The problem is compounded by inconsistencies across different websites that use similar fonts, such as Ponomar.net. The character in question often appears between two characters but remains on top of the previous one, as noted in the source from Ponomar.net.
- ❖ **Semantic Impact:** One of the critical issues raised is whether the incorrect positioning of U+0483 affects the meaning of words. If the misplacement does alter meaning, the next step would be to identify a technical solution to correct the positioning of the character in all environments consistently.

Overall, further exploration of how each font manages the combining Cyrillic titlo is required. An ideal font needs to be identified or custom modifications made to resolve these rendering problems. The potential solution could be a mapping table that would relate this non-standard Unicode (PUA) rendering to the accepted standard form. The other solution could be a script or tool that, within applications using LaTeX, PDF generation tools, and Python environments, acts to adjust the font's behavior.

d. Mapping Table Solution for PUA Characters

We adopt an approach, implemented in Python, aiming to create a mapping table as part of our attempt to solve the rendering issues of Unicode combining characters in general. The aim is to remap PUA characters before any further analysis or processing of Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic texts. The approach has followed the following steps:

- ❖ **Mapping Table Creation:** A custom mapping table was designed in order to map PUA characters like `\\uE001` to their respective Unicode counterparts like, for instance, `U+0438`. That ensures the accurate representation in all platforms and environments. The mapping is shown in Table 1.

<i>The actual character on the website</i>	<i>Modified due to PUA font</i>	<i>Replacement /Suggestion</i>	<i>Unicode</i>
	H	U+0438	
	Ђ	U+0483	
	Ч	U+0427	
	€	U+0464	
	Ы	U+A651	
	H	H U+0418	
	Ѓ	U+223B	

Fig. 11: Re-Mapping Table

- ❖ **Python Program Implementation:** A customized Python function was designed to iterate through the input text and remap all appearances of PUA characters based on the mapping table. This preprocessing step permitted us to tackle problematic characters more effectively, ensuring that the text is properly processed before further computational analysis.

As shown in figure 12, PUA characters appeared inconsistently, with `U+0483` being particularly compromised in environments like PyCharm and LibreOffice [9]. After applying our approach, most of the characters are correctly displayed, as shown in the figure below.

Fig. 12: Before Mapping PUA characters appeared inconsistently, particularly compromised in environments like PyCharm

Fig. 13: After Mapping visualized correctly in all tested environments, ensuring consistency and preserving the semantic integrity of the textual data.

Organizing the Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic Corpus

The organization of the collected data is a crucial and extremely important step for the computational analysis of Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic texts. Structuring the data has provided a better understanding about the size of the corpus, sources, and current limitations. As said above, our corpus is assembled from various scattered, often remote, and hardly accessible archives, digital libraries, and manuscript collections. However, besides raw texts, we have also started seeking and collecting annotated parts of the corpus. Currently, we have collected over 300k annotated words [10], each corresponding to its lemma, morphology, and parts of speech tags. While the number of annotated data is limited, it has proven to be a very useful resource for syntactic analysis, morphological, parts of speech tagging, and lemmatization. While the quantity of this annotated data remains comparatively small, it will be increased through collaborations with linguistic experts, as well as by developing automated tools able to assist in the annotation process.

We know that structuring and organizing the corpus not only would make easier to perform computational tasks on Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic case but also gives the necessary basis for both raw and annotated corpus expansion. We further plan to develop the dataset, considering the improvement in quality and accessibility of materials, which will serve as a valuable resource for reaching an improvement of the linguistic analysis..

Sanskrit

Igor Spanò identified and analyzed several databases of digitized texts in Sanskrit literature to create a suitable corpus of texts to compare with the text of the Creed. Among the various databases available, Igor Spanò chose to use the Digital Corpus of Sanskrit (<http://www.sanskrit-linguistics.org/dcs/>), which contains a considerable number of Sanskrit texts already lemmatised and

not, as a starting point for the creation of the reference corpus. A choice was made between the texts, with a large proportion of those already lemmatised being included in the reference Corpus in the first place. With the collected data, Irfan Ali was able to start training a machine learning model program for Sanskrit which is going to be described in detail at paragraph 3. If the training process will have success we could be able to offer a state-of-the-art tool, for philologists and historians of religions, and in general for all those working in the field of religious studies, Indological disciplines, and linguistics.

Arabic

Regarding the Arabic language, there are currently no online corpora of digitized texts belonging to the Arab-Christian tradition. The corpus is almost entirely unpublished and the translations of the Symbolum into Arabic are preserved in manuscripts spread throughout the world.

Fig. 14: Elias of Nisibis, Commentary on Creed. BAV, MS 143

Before the digital development of the IT section of the project, it was therefore essential to proceed with the identification of the sources and their partial acquisition. In the first instance, a cooperation was activated with the Palermo unit of the PRIN 2020 project *The Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed and its translations. First exploration and methodological verification of a transdisciplinary research on the symbol of the Councils in history, culture and society (4th-20th century)*. In particular, the initial part of the work was shared with the post-doc researcher Anna Canton who, in the same way, was tracing the manuscript tradition of the Symbolum in Arabic.

A database was thus jointly created containing all the data extracted from the available and accessible catalogues, both online and on paper, and from the reference bibliography. The table was thus divided into: Country, City and Library where the *codex* is preserved, cataloguing number, place where it was copied, date and copyist, foliation/pagination. Considering that the text of the Symbolum can be found in a wide variety of formats, an additional string was inserted concerning the editorial location of the text: miscellany, dialogic text, catechism, commentary, canonical collection,

exposition of doctrines, Profession of faith, Ecumenical Council, etc. Finally, a column was added relating to the confessional typology of belonging: Chaldean, Coptic, Latin, Maronite, Melkite, Syriac, etc.

ITALY	Rome	Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana (BAV)	Vat. Ar. 149	Arabic	Egypt, 1372		Coptic	Nomocanon	186 ss; 216v-220r	Mai, 275		
ITALY	Rome	Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana (BAV)	Vat. Ar. 154	Arabic	Sidone (Lebanon)- Aleppo (Syria), XIV (?)		Melkite	Liber sacrarum synodorum	117v-118v; 114v-115v	Mai, 291		
ITALY	Rome	Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana (BAV)	Vat. Ar. 158	Arabic	Egypt, 1356-1357	Expositio fidei a Patribus (Nicaenis) trecentist decem octo pronuntiate	Coptic		148r-157v	Mai, 298-299		Author: Abū al-Majd ibn Yuhanna
ITALY	Rome	Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana (BAV)	Vat. Ar. 450	Arabic	XIV-XV		Melkite	Psalterium secundum usum ecclesiae Melchitarum	17rv-18r	Mai, 519		

Fig. 15: Symbolum: Table of MSS

When the database was created, four witnesses were selected, based on a temporal range (12th-14th century), and then transcribed. From these transcriptions, some key terms were extracted in order to perform a semantic search within the *corpus*. *Kitab* currently includes 10,200 text files with the corresponding metadata and provides a digital toolbox and the instruments to empower users to explore Arabic texts in completely new ways and to expand the frontiers of knowledge about one of the world's largest and most complex textual traditions.

The OpenITI corpus contains more than 30 Gb of text, of different kinds and spanning different ages. The availability of such a large corpus is a valuable resource, by inspecting it one can look for evidence of language evolution over time, nevertheless, working with large corpora poses several technical challenges that will be tackled along the WP4 arabic workflow.

2. PoS tagging techniques

Latin

Available Tools

The more the text is explicit in its main features, the better results the study tools can offer. To express internal relations of the text such as grammar, morphology, syntax, dependencies to number some, a specifically trained recognition tool is required. Nowadays, more than one digital tool is available to achieve PoS tagging. Among them, WP₄ has tried the pipeline offered on [WebLithc](#) during our last ITSERR training in June. One can also count [ANNIS toolkit](#), [Morpheus](#) from Perseus, and [Lindat](#). After a few initial tries, Federico Iezzi and Elia Scapini have come to consider Lindat as outperforming compared to others and therefore, we consider using this tool. There's also a parser offered by Stanford through the [Stanza suite](#) which is trained stochastically, we plan to exploit also this tool.

Tagging the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed

To help the latin model (see below chapter 3) in detecting semantic similarity to the main elements of the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed and also to test the capabilities of the sistem to guess wheter a term in the corpus refers or not to the target term of the Creed, we needed a disambiguated number of sentences as a golden standard. Therefore Elia Scapini and Federico Iezzi have composed some synsets on the three persons of the Trinity to apply as query integration.

As a starting point, latin synsets can be found on [Latin WordNet](#), an on-going project of the University of Exeter in collaboration with the University of Geneva, under the direction of William Michael Short, to create a comprehensive lexico-semantic database of the Latin language. Here, synsets for "Pater", "Filius", and "Spiritus", though, present several deficiencies that need to be taken into account and fixed. For example, of the various synsets associated with "Pater", WP₄ is only interested in #o6889800, which is "God when considered as the first person in the Trinity", containing terms like "genitor", "parens" that can be excluded from the query while "creator" could be retained. A similar argument applies to "Son" and "Spirit", the first being poor in synsets, the second even too rich but without Trinity-related records. To fill these gaps, we plan to carry out a comparison with one of the services offered on [SSHOC](#) (Social Services and Humanities Open Marketplace), a hub that collects various IT tools for language studies. Among these, we find [CoPhiWordNet](#), a tool created by Riccardo del Gratta (CNR-ILC) that allows users to view the descriptors of synsets linked to the typed word. Staying with the example of "Pater", the synset card relating to "God understood as the first person of the Trinity" has ID #109536973 and is specified in #1001109536973 for the Greek language and in #1002109536973 for the Latin language. This means that the reference synset #109536973 is specified language by language (1001 and 1002, for Greek and Latin respectively), thus constituting an additional resource for comparison. Even here, however, it will be necessary to draw critically, integrating and eliminating meanings foreign to the Creed. Once completed, this work on synsets will be returned to the IT team to assess the best way to proceed.

Example of tagging work:

```
credo in unum deum, <REF 5
status="OK">patrem</REF 5> <REF 5
status="OK">omnipotentem</REF 5>, <REF 5
```

Example of an element in the synset of "God understood as the first person of the Trinity"

```
{
"lemma": "creator",
```

<pre>status="OK">factorem</REF 5> caeli et terrae, visibilium omnium et invisibilium. Quaeso, inquit, <REF 5 status="NO">Pater</REF 5> sanctissime, permitte mihi ut meas iniquitates defleam</pre>	<pre>"pos": "n", "morpho": "n-s---mn3-", "uri": "c4275", "prosody": "creator" }</pre>
---	---

Fig. 18: Examples of tagging process and of a synset on the Father

Ancient Greek

Along with Latin, PoS tagging for Ancient Greek has largely been performed in a rule-based manner by Morpheus, the tool available in Perseus and launched by Gregory Crane (1991). It has been shown that this tool has a few limitations especially connected with the challenge of guessing an uncertain output. We have also tested the [Parser trained and released with Ancient-Greek BERT](#) and the aforementioned Stanza textual preprocessing tool (see 2.1).

An example follows of how PoS tagging is realized both by the parser of Ancient Greek BERT and that of Stanford - Stanza. Both of them consist of probabilistic models and differ in their predictions. In this case, Stanza shows its probabilistic training predicting that the first term for “light”, φῶς, is a neuter term, while the second is wrongly considered masculine. On the other hand, Stanza shows to possess a larger number of features, including word dependencies.

<pre>Parser Ancient-Greek-BERT input: sentence = Sentence("φῶς ἐκ φωτός") tagger.predict(sentence) print(sentence)</pre>	<pre>Parser Stanza input: doc = nlp("φῶς ἐκ φωτός") print(doc) print(doc.entities) [[{ "id": 1, "text": "φῶς", "lemma": "φῶς", "upos": "NOUN", "xpos": "n-s---na-", "feats": "Case=Acc Gender=Neut Number=Sing", "head": 3, "deprel": "obl", "start_char": 0, "end_char": 3 }, { "id": 2, "text": "ἐκ", "lemma": "ἐκ", "upos": "ADP", "xpos": "r-----", "head": 3, "deprel": "case", "start_char": 4, "end_char": 6 }, { "id": 3, "text": "φωτός", "lemma": "φῶς", "upos": "NOUN",</pre>
<pre>Sentence[3]: "φῶς ἐκ φωτός" → ["φῶς"/n-s---nn-, "ἐκ"/r-----, "φωτός"/n-s---ng-]</pre>	

```

        "xpos": "n-s---mg-",
        "feats":
    "Case=Gen|Gender=Masc|Number=Sing",
        "head": 0,
        "deprel": "root",
        "start_char": 7,
        "end_char": 12,
    "misc": "SpaceAfter=No"
    }
  ]
]
[]

```

Fig. 19: Examples of PoS tagging from AGBERT and Stanza

Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic

Considering the limited texts annotated with lemmas, we have started working on an automatic lemmatization system for Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic texts. Lemmatization is the process of reducing words to their base or root or dictionary form, known as the lemma. This step is essential to handle the complex inflectional morphology of Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic and is generally one of the preliminary text processing operations used in NLP to solve complex tasks. Because of the richness of grammatical structure in this language, creating a correct and reliable lemmatizer is quite indispensable for further computational treatment, such as syntactic analysis, and research into historical linguistics.

Our lemmatization research work is constrained due to the limited size of available annotated data, however, we do use this data to train and refine our dictionary-based model. By increasing the annotated corpus and improving the lemmatization algorithms, we struggle to develop a robust system that can handle the critical and complex morphological variations within Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic texts. This automated lemmatization tool will form the base of future linguistic analyses and open the door to more advanced computational studies, allowing researchers to explore the language's structure in greater depth and with increased precision and knowledge.

We are currently working on a novel dictionary-based approach. This approach is to be designed bearing in mind the complexities posed by the language's inflectional and complex morphology. Using a learned dictionary, our model will automatically reduce words to their base or root forms, hence facilitating further computational analysis.

Our system would be used not only as a tool for lemmatization but also in the expansion of the annotated dataset. As the model is improved, it would be of great support in the automation of the annotation process, considerably increasing the amount of annotated data. This will enhance not only the accuracy of the Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic texts' analysis but also the possibility of further linguistic research by offering scholars a larger and more accurate corpus for study.

Sanskrit

As far as the lemmatization process is concerned, since many Sanskrit texts, although digitized, have not yet been lemmatized, and to explore the possibility of expanding the reference corpus and thus improving research, a digital tool is being created to separate the *sandhis* present in Sanskrit texts and then proceed to lemmatize the individual terms. The phonetic phenomenon of *sandhi* consists of

include tokenization of the text, *sandhis'* splitting, and consequently recognition of the phonetic changes that individual lemmas usually undergo. In parallel, Irfan Ali conducted the analysis of the Sanskrit translation of the Creed, using machine learning approaches in Python once again. In order to reach the semantic level, he is developing a program to identify and divide internal *sandhis* and thus isolate and separate verbal root forms or pure thematic states of nouns and adjectives.

Indeed, concerning the analysis of the reference Corpus of texts and the Sanskrit translation of the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed, as we have already noted Sanskrit shows several linguistic phenomena that complicate its automatic analysis. Sanskrit is an inflected language. The roles of words in a sentence (such as subject, object, and verb) are indicated by the endings (inflections) of the words rather than by their order. The Sanskrit language also lacks proper datasets for analysis. The scarcity of large, annotated datasets for Sanskrit poses significant challenges for linguistic and computational analysis for tokenization, sandhi splitting of compound words, lemmatization, morphological analysis, synonym finding, text normalization, part of speech tagging (PoS), etc. using machine learning methods in Python. The digitization of Sanskrit texts has not progressed as much as for some other classical languages. There is a lack of standardized, comprehensive, and annotated *corpora*. Annotated *corpora*, where texts are marked with information about their syntactic structure, semantics, etc., are essential for developing and training natural language processing (NLP) models using Python. Efforts to create such *corpora* are under study, but challenges are faced due to the linguistic complexity and variability of Sanskrit texts. The complexity of Sanskrit's grammar, including its extensive use of compounds, Sandhi rules, and inflectional morphology, poses significant challenges for computational processing. Developing algorithms that can handle these features requires detailed linguistic resources and expertise, which are still being developed for Sanskrit.

We analyzed the Digital Corpus of Sanskrit (DCS) repository for corpus collection to extract and build the dataset from different available Sanskrit books and texts to train the model. The DCS is designed for text-historical research in Sanskrit linguistics and philology. This repository contains various religious books, poems, etc. that help in the dataset collection. We extracted the following information from this repository, as shown in the table below.

Total text/books	257
Total no. of chapters in a whole	14578
Total number of Words or Lemmas	5360303

Fig. 21: Extracted Information

Every book has a different number of chapters. Each chapter has a different id number. In this, each chapter has a separate naming convention to identify the individual chapter like the following:

The file name "**Aṣṭāṅgahr̥dayasaṃhitā-0007-AHS, Sū., 8-1162**" means, Title of the Text=Aṣṭāṅgahr̥dayasaṃhitā, chapter seven ("0007"), citation form of the chapter name="AHS, Sū., 8", chapter id="1162".

All the Sanskrit text contains various entries and looks unstructured and messy for developing the dataset for our project. We organized and preprocessed the ancient Sanskrit language text from the Digital Corpus of Sanskrit (DCS) using Python to transform messy, unstructured, and raw textual data into a format that can be effectively used to train machine learning models, leading to better results and usability of the text data for subsequent analysis or modeling.

We merged all the books, sentences, words, lemmas, etc., and then we obtained the data for only sentences, words, and lemmas for applying the various operations in Python after removing the irrelevant data as the sample is shown below in Figure 22.

```
## text: Abhidhānacintāmaṇi
# text = praṇipatyārḥataḥ siddhasāṅgaśabdānuśāsaṇaḥ
1   praṇipatya      praṇipat
2   ārḥataḥ   ārḥata
3   siddha   sidh
4   sāṅga   sāṅga
5   śabda   śabda
6   anuśāsaṇaḥ      anuśāsana
# text = rūḍhayaugikamiśrāṇām nāmnām mālām tanomyaham
1   rūḍha   ruh
2   yaugika yaugika
3   miśrāṇām      miśra|
4   nāmnām   nāman
5   mālām   mālā
6   tanomi   tan
7   aham     mad
# text = vyutpattirahitāḥ śabdā rūḍhā ākhaṇḍalādayaḥ
1   vyutpatti      vyutpatti
2   rahitāḥ   rahita
3   śabdā     śabda
4   rūḍhā     ruh
5   ākhaṇḍala      ākhaṇḍala
6   ādayaḥ     ādi
```

Fig. 22: Sample of Extracted Sentences, Words, and Lemmas from Sanskrit Books

Next, we only extracted the useful data using Python such as word and lemma in CSV file for developing the dataset from the whole document as the sample is shown below in Figure 23.

We also separated all sentences from all 14578 chapters of books and merged them in a single file to process using Python for various operations to be performed on them like tokenization, lemmatization, etc. The sample of the extracted information is shown below in Figure 24.

word, lemma
om, om
namo, namas
buddhāya, buddha
yaḥ, yad
sarvathā, sarvathā
sarva, sarva
hata, han
andhakāraḥ, andhakāra
saṃsāra, saṃsāra
pañkāt, pañka
jagant, jagant
ujjahāra, uddhṛ
tasmai, tad
namaskṛtya, namaskṛ
yathā, yathā
artha, artha
śāstre, śāstra
śāstram, śāstra
pravakṣyāmi, pravac
abhidharmakośam, abhidharmakośa
prajñā, prajñā
amalā, amala

Fig. 23: Sample of Extracted Words, Lemmas from Sanskrit Books

prajñāmalā sānucarābhidharmāḥ tatprāptaye yāpi ca yacca śāstram
tasyārthato'smin samanupraveśāt sa cāśrayo 'syetyabhidharmakośam
dharmāṇāṃ pravīcayamantareṇa nāsti kleśānāṃ yata upasāntaye'bhyupāyaḥ
kleśaiśca bhramati bhavārṇave'tra lokastaddhetorata uditaḥ kilaiṣa śāstrā
sāsravānāsravā dharmāḥ saṃskṛtā mārgavarjitāḥ
sāsravāḥ āsravāsteṣu yasmāt samanūserate
anāsravā mārgasatyam trividham cāpyasaṃskṛtam
ākāśam dvau nirodhau ca tatrākāśam anāvṛtiḥ
pratisaṃkhyānirodho yo viśaṃyogaḥ pṛthak pṛthak
utpādāntavighno'nyo nirodho'pratisaṃkhyayā
te punaḥ saṃskṛtā dharmā rūpādiskandhapañcakam
ta evādhvā kathāvastu saniḥsārāḥ savastukāḥ
ye sāsravā upādānaskandhāste saraṇā api
duḥkham samudayo loko dṛṣṭisthānam bhavaśca te
rūpaṃ pañcendriyāṇyarthāḥ pañcāvijñaptireva ca
tadvijñānāśrayā rūpapasādāścaḥsurādayaḥ
rūpaṃ dvidhā viṃśatidhā śabdastvaṣṭavidhaḥ rasaḥ
śoḍhā caturvidho gandhaḥ spṛśyamekādaśātmakam
vikṣiptācittakasyāpi yo'nubandhaḥ śubhāśubhaḥ
mahābhūtānyupādāya sa hyavijñaptirucyate
bhūtāni pṛthividhāturaptejovāyudhātavaḥ
dṛṣṭyādikarmasaṃsiddhāḥ kharasnehoṣṇaterāṇāḥ
pṛthivī varṇasaṃsthānamucyate lokasaṃjñayā
āpastejaśca vāyustu dhātoreva tathāpi ca
indriyārthāsta eveṣṭā daśāyatanadhātavaḥ
vedanānubhavaḥ saṃjñā nimittodgrahaṇātmikā
caturbhyo'nye tu saṃskāraskandhaḥ ete punastrayaḥ
dharmāyatanadhātvākhyāḥ sahāvijñaptiyasaṃskṛtaiḥ
vijñānaṃ prativijñaptiḥ mana āyatanaṃ ca tat

Fig. 24: Sample of Extracted Sentences only from Sanskrit Books

One of the features that makes Sanskrit more complicated to process is the use of compound words obtained from phonetic word unification. In order to comprehend the meaning of the compound word, identify the words that compose it and therefore split the compound word into its component words.

For *sandhis'* splitting of compound words of the Sanskrit language, we also built a new dataset using Python from different books of the Digital Corpus of Sanskrit repository containing a total number of compound words equal to 96535. This helped us to enhance the available dataset for experimental purposes. The sample is shown below in Figure 25.

compound, split
tatprāptaye, tad+prāptaye
pravīcavāntareṇa, pravīcavam+antareṇa
mārgavarjītāḥ, mārga+varjītāḥ
sāsravāḥ, sa+āsravāḥ
evādhvā, eva+adhvā
kathāvastu, kathā+vastu
saniḥsārāḥ, sa+niḥsārāḥ
dṛṣṭīsthānam, dṛṣṭi+sthānam
yoanubandhaḥ, yaḥ+anubandhaḥ
śubhāśubhaḥ, śubha+aśubhaḥ
vāyustu, vāyuḥ+tu
dhātureva, dhātuḥ+eva
yaddhi, yat+hi
cakṣurādīnām, cakṣus+ādīnām
vedanāsaṃjñe, vedanā+saṃjñe
kramoathavā, kramaḥ+athavā
ekamāyatanam, ekam+āyatanam
śāstrapramāṇā, śāstra+pramāṇāḥ
ityeke, iti+eke
skandhādīnām, skandha+ādīnām

Fig. 25: Sample of Extracted Compound and Split Words from Sanskrit Books

Tokenization of Sanskrit Text

We worked on the tokenization of the Sanskrit text using Python. The data was taken from the Agnipurāṇa book which was extracted from the Digital Corpus of Sanskrit (DCS). We arranged input in sentence form as given below in Figure 26 to test how the compiler behaves.

a. Tools used for Tokenization

We employed Python libraries such as iNLTK and IndicNLP for this purpose. These two libraries offer various tokenization methods including character level, word level, or sub-word level as shown in Figures 27 and 28 respectively.

śriyaṃ sarasvatīm gaurīm gaṇeśaṃ skandamīśvaram
brahmāṇaṃ vahnimindrādīn vāsudevaṃ namāmyaham
naimiṣe harimījānā ṛṣayaḥ śaunakādayaḥ
tīrthayātrāprasaṅgena svāgataṃ sūtamabruvan
ṛṣaya ūcuḥ
sūta tvaṃ pūjito'smābhiḥ sārātsāraṃ vadasva naḥ
yena vijñānamātreṇasarvvajñatvaṃ prajāyate
sūta uvāca
sārātsāro hi bhagavān viṣṇuḥ sargādikṛdvibhuḥ
brahmāhamasmi taṃ jñātvā sarvvajñatvaṃ prajāyate
dve brahmaṇī veditavye śabdabrahma paraṃ ca yat
dve vidye veditavye hi iti cātharvaṇī śrutih
ahaṃ śukraśca pailādyā gatvā vadarikāśramam
vyāsaṃ natvā pṛṣṭavantaḥ so'smān sāramathābravit
vyāsa uvāca
śukādyaiḥ śrṅṅu sūta tvaṃ vaśiṣṭho mām yathā'bravit
brahmasāraṃ hi pṛcchantaṃ munibhiśca parātparam
vasiṣṭha uvāca
dvaividhyaṃ brahmā vakṣyāmi śrṅṅu vyāsākhilānugam
yathā'gnirmām purā prāha munibhirdaivataih saha
purāṇaṃ paramāgneyaṃ brahmavidyākṣaraṃ param
ṛgvedādyaparaṃ brahma sarvadevasukhāvaham
agninoktaṃ purāṇaṃ yadāgneyaṃ brahmasammitam
bhuktimuktupradaṃ divyaṃ paṭhatāṃ śrṅṅvatāṃ nṛṇām
vasiṣṭha uvāca
saṃsārasāgarottāranāvaṃ brahmeśvaraṃ veda
vidyāsāraṃ yadviditvā sarvajño jāyate naraḥ
agniruvāca
viṣṇuḥ kālāgnirudro'haṃ vidyāsāraṃ vadāmi te
vidyāsāraṃ purāṇaṃ yatsarvaṃ sarvasya kāraṇam
sargasya pratisargasya vaṃśamanvantarasya ca
vaṃśānucaritādeśca matsyakūrmādirūpadhṛk

Fig. 26: Sample of Data for Tokenization of the Sanskrit Text

```
[ 'śriyaṃ', 'sarasvatīm', 'gaurīm', 'gaṇeśaṃ', 'skandamīśvaram' ]
[ 'brahmāṇaṃ', 'vahnimindrādīn', 'vāsudevaṃ', 'namāmyaham' ]
[ 'naimiṣe', 'harimījānā', 'ṛṣayaḥ', 'śaunakādayaḥ' ]
[ 'tīrthayātrāprasaṅgena', 'svāgataṃ', 'sūtamabruvan' ]
[ 'ṛṣaya', 'ūcuḥ' ]
[ 'sūta', 'tvaṃ', 'pūjito', '', 'smābhiḥ', 'sārātsāraṃ', 'vadasva', 'naḥ' ]
[ 'yena', 'vijñānamātreṇasarvvajñatvaṃ', 'prajāyate' ]
[ 'sūta', 'uvāca' ]
[ 'sārātsāro', 'hi', 'bhagavān', 'viṣṇuḥ', 'sargādikṛdvibhuḥ' ]
[ 'brahmāhamasmi', 'taṃ', 'jñātvā', 'sarvvajñatvaṃ', 'prajāyate' ]
[ 'dve', 'brahmaṇī', 'veditavye', 'śabdabrahma', 'paraṃ', 'ca', 'yat' ]
[ 'dve', 'vidye', 'veditavye', 'hi', 'iti', 'cātharvaṇī', 'śrutih' ]
```

Fig. 27: Sample of Tokenization of the Sanskrit Text at Word Level using Python

agnim ile purohitam
yajñasya devam ṛtvijam
hotāram ratnadhātāmam
agnih pūrvebhiḥ ṛṣibhiḥ
īdyaḥ nūtanaiḥ uta
sa devān ā iha vakṣati
agninā rayim aśnavat
poṣam eva divedive
yaśasam vīravattāmam
agne yam yajñam adhvaram
viśvataḥ paribhūḥ asi
saḥ it deveṣu gacchati
agnih hotā kavikratuḥ
satyaḥ citraśravastamaḥ
devaḥ devebhiḥ ā gamat
yat aṅga dāśuṣe tvam
agne bhadram kariṣyasi
tava it tat satyam aṅgiraḥ
upa tvā agne divedive
doṣāvastar dhiyā vayam
namaḥ bharantaḥ ā imasi
rājantam adhvarāṇām
gopām ṛtasya dīdivim
vardhamānam sve dame

Fig. 30: Sample of Lemmatization Data of the Sanskrit Text

3. Word embedding extraction

Latin and Ancient Greek

Premise, state of the art, further steps

The craft of embedding Latin and Ancient Greek comprises a challenge that has to do with both these two languages, is always more relevant in the NLP pipeline of ancient mediterranean languages and is now collecting attention from scholars and in the literature. We are referring to including morphological and syntactical information in the embedding process. Encoders are normally trained for isolating contemporary languages, (mostly English). Isolating languages tend to place information in the order of the words while, on the contrary, inflected languages such as Ancient Greek and Latin, tend to give less relevance to where a word is located in the phrase and more to how the term is inflected (morphology). This entails for example that, in Ancient Greek and Latin, a genitive can be placed quite far from its regent word. These languages not only have cases, a highly refined morphology and the order of words is less relevant, we also possess much less tokens: modern languages are stored nowadays in the order of many billion tokens while, for Ancient Greek and Latin, we possess tokens in the order of millions in the luckiest of the cases. In sum, NLP for Ancient mediterranean languages requires a different approach in the embedding process.

Techniques in NLP for ancient languages like CNN for NLP (Convolutional Neural Networks), RNN (Recurrent Neural Networks), LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory), FastText, GloVe (Global Vectors for Word Representation) and Word2Vec evolve fastly, for a smart review we recommend chapter 23 and 24 of the fourth edition of the AI manual by Russel and Norvig (ref. 10).

Nowadays, BERT models (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) fit into the NLP area by around 2019. BERT and its successors represent a significant evolution in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP) thanks to their ability to understand the context of words within a text, an ability that is crucial when analyzing languages with a rich morphology such as Latin and Ancient Greek. BERT-based models utilize the Transformer architecture, which is distinguished by the use of attention and self-attention mechanisms and was first published in 2017 by Vaswani et al (ref. 14). These mechanisms allow the model to weight the relative importance of each word in the context in which it appears, thus offering a deeper semantic understanding of the text.

The structure of BERT consists of several layers of Transformers. Typically, the base version of BERT is structured in 12 Transformer layers, with 12 attention heads each, while the "large" version contains 24. Each layer processes the input received from the previous layer, adding a level of contextual understanding.

One of the distinctive features of BERT is the use of special tokens, including the [CLS] (Classification) token. This token is added at the beginning of each input sequence and serves as a context aggregator for the entire sequence. The output vector corresponding to the [CLS] token is then used for classification tasks, having captured relevant information from the entire sequence.

After becoming familiar with state-of-the-art BERT tools (we name them in the following sub-paragraphs according to the languages they perform on) we are beginning to draw up a list of experiments to try to open up room for improvement in the embedding process. Since this field is exquisitely empirical, among our improvement experiments we suggest trying to add to the embedding process also morphological and syntactical information, eventually tailing them to the word vectors in the best position (layer) possible. To try to achieve this, we are trying to start an

exchange with experts in the field. To name some: Alek Keersmaekers, Digital Humanist in Leuven and curator of different projects in the field; Alessandro Lenci, professor of computational linguistics and author of several papers on the topic. This unedited approach could be helpful due to the lack of Latin and Ancient Greek data and their highly inflected nature. We also consider exploring state-of-the-art techniques, like embedding distillation (Krahn 2023) or sBERT models.

Latin encoders

More than one Latin encoder is nowadays publicly available. Among them, we tried [Latin BERT](#). For research purposes, the IT team of Marcella Cornia developed and exploited two latin models that are now available [in the HuggingFace space dedicated to the ITSERR project](#). Last June 2024, IT Team presented some first qualitative results in semantic attribution. These initial results were obtained comparing the capacity of the two models to tell whether some words were referring to the three persons of the Trinity or not in reference to a number of fragments annotated by Federico Iezzi and Elia Scapini.

Ancient Greek encoders

The most well-known and widespread encoder for Ancient Greek is [Ancient-Greek-BERT](#). This was released in 2021 and accompanied by a paper co-authored by Pranaydeep Singh, Gorik Rutten and Els Lefever. With them, we are testing and comparing also [Logion BERT, released in 2023](#), the [SHLM-grc-en](#) released by Krahn in 2023, distilled from an English large model and subsequently finetuned and also GreBERTa and PhilBERTa by [Riemenschneider and Frank 2023](#).

Semantic similarity retrieval for Ancient Greek

We are working to exploit these BERT encoders in order to embed both the Eustathian corpus above mentioned and x-from-x expressions to retrieve these statements in the text with other closely related statements.

The expression «x-from-x» collects formulas such as God from God, Light from Light, true God from true God, and it was broadly used in the 4th century, especially if compounded into faith formulas. X-from-x statements appear in 4th-century authors of diverse doctrinal positions and from different contexts, they also appear in the first part of the second article of some 4th-century credal statements. The context of major comparison of x-from-x formulas is the debate on the relation of Father and Son and was prompted by the shared necessity to fix the common faith of the Church into synodically agreed statements. Rule based retrieval, e.g. that offered by Thesaurus Linguae Graecae (TLG) would fail in reporting all the x-from-x statements of a corpus, since this kind of search does not include in the input all the possible lemmas functioning as x. We think that a more stochastic approach could fix this problem, offering a new kind of search process for Ancient Greek to be, eventually, developed into a software. We are working to embed the Eustathian corpus and one or more input phrases, such as the greek expressions for *Light from Light* or *God from God*. Once embedded and turned into vectors, a cosine-similarity tool will retrieve the expressions of the corpus more related to the input sentences.

Few exploratory tests were made and several work stages were passed through by Elia Scapini and Federico Iezzi from September 2024 to present (end of October 2024), working with a small corpus from Eustathius to which were added some expressions of Arius and other x-from-x statements of 4th-century faith formulae.

The first version of the software was able to compare the similarity of two sentences, e.g. “Θεὸν ἐκ Θεοῦ” against “συμμόρφους τοῦ υἱοῦ τοῦ θεοῦ” and to report a similarity percentage. The second version was implemented to compare an Input_sentence to a corpus of sentences separated by a comma and to reorder the list of phrases in order of similarity. Then, we hypothesized that adding a second Input_sentence2 and asking the model to retrieve the most similar phrases from the corpus to vectors of Input_sentence1 + Input_sentence2 could have led to better results. The core idea of this last test is that the final user should be able to add as much information as he desires to the searched sentence in order to precise the retrieval target. The aim would be to open to a final Input_sentenceN where n sentences can be added and are summed into a single vector. The first results from version three were slightly positive, encouraging to prosecute with the search job but, at the same time, still imprecise, since the model was mixing correct similarities with doubtful ones. The turning point came after showing our model to the IT Team. Davide Caffagni and Federico Cocchi, both Ph.D. students members of Marcella Cornia’s team suggested to perform a change in the code passing by “cls_vector = model_output.last_hidden_state[:, 0, :]” to “cls_vector = model_output.pooler_output”. This modifies how the CLS (classification) vector is extracted from the model's output. Using pooler output is convenient for a more processed and potentially better-performing CLS vector, especially for downstream tasks like classification. Once this change was applied, the new model outperformed the former. We show here some initial results by testing the fourth version of the software: the number of phrases in the corpus was 200, here only expected high similarity retrievals are shown.

Corpus: 200 phrases	We look for statements as close as possible to x-from-x statements from NC Input_phrase1+Input_phrase2	Results: 20 closest phrases
ὅλον ἐξ ὅλου, μόνον ἐκ μόνου, τέλειον ἐκ τελείου, βασιλέα ἐκ βασιλέως, κύριον ἀπὸ κυρίου λύχνον ἀπὸ λύχνου ὅμοιοι ἐξ ὁμοίων ...	φῶς ἐκ φωτός, θεὸν ἀληθινὸν ἐκ θεοῦ ἀληθινοῦ Other phrases exploited during the tests θεὸν εκ θεοῦ	σῶμα ὧν ὁρατὸν - Similarità: 0.6608242392539978 ὅλον ἐξ ὅλου, μόνον ἐκ μόνου, τέλειον ἐκ τελείου, - Similarità: 0.6123228669166565 τροπὰς ὑποφαίνει ρητὰς - Similarità: 0.5908013582229614 λύχνον ἀπὸ λύχνου - Similarità: 0.5880970358848572 ὑπὸ τοῦ πατρὸς διὰ τοῦ υἱοῦ - Similarità: 0.5880355834960938 μακάριε πάπα - Similarità: 0.5874956250190735 τὸν υἱὸν τοῦ θεοῦ μονογενῆ - Similarità: 0.5797213315963745 ἀλλ’ ὡς μονὰς καὶ ἀρχὴ πάντων - Similarità: 0.578707218170166 ὅμοιοι ἐξ ὁμοίων - Similarità: 0.5723357796669006 βασιλέα ἐκ βασιλέως, - Similarità: 0.5712873339653015 τοῦτον θεὸν γεννήσαντα υἱὸν μονογενῆ πρὸ χρόνων αἰώνων - Similarità: 0.5680366158485413 οὐδ’ ἄχρι τινὸς ἐννοίας τοῦτο φαντασιώσαι τῆς ψυχῆς δυναμένης - Similarità: 0.5678119659423828 τὴν ἀσώματον Σοφίαν οἰόμεθα χραίνεσθαι - Similarità: 0.5675251483917236

		<p>ὑπὸ πάντων προσκυνεῖται - Similarità: 0.566463053226471 κύριον ἀπὸ κυρίου - Similarità: 0.5662023425102234 Τὸν παθόντα τοιγαροῦν Ἰησοῦν Κύριον ἐποίησε - Similarità: 0.5616821050643921 Τὸν παθόντα τοιγαροῦν Ἰησοῦν Κύριον ἐποίησε - Similarità: 0.5616821050643921 ἄλλο δὲ τὴν εἰκόνα αὐτοῦ - Similarità: 0.5528856515884399 ὑποστήσαντα ἰδίῳ θελήματι ἄτρεπτον καὶ ἀναλλοίωτον κτίσματοῦ θεοῦ τέλειον - Similarità: 0.5516977906227112 διὸ δὴ ὁ κύριος ἡμῶν - Similarità: 0.549056887626648</p>
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Fig. 31: Exploratory results of sentence retrieval with AGBERT

We also pursued various tests, especially dedicated to detecting which list of layers best reduces noise and represents the semantic similarity. It's nowadays common to consider the first layers (from 1 to 4) more related to grammar and morphology while the last ones closer to semantic tasks. Besides the choice of which and how many layers to adopt, BERT models offer scholars several options to customize the encoder to their own purposes in order to focus the expected output: vectors can be summed, averaged, queued with size regularization, or other solutions still can be adopted. One has also the possibility to select token vectors and collect them, or to stick to the CLS vectors.

From our initial exploration, a certain number of adjustments is emerging as desirable. If it were possible, we'd need to understand why the model reports as similar expressions that we don't agree with, and vice versa. Punctuation marks are also an unexpected concern: the model reports different similarities on the basis of them (this is why, in the example above, Input_phrase1 "φῶς ἐκ φωτός," contains a comma). Another issue is that phrases are embedded one by one, with the problem of opening and closing of sentences. The consequent risk is to fail the retrieval process if the target expressions in the corpus were splitted in two phrases. Besides these issues to fix, we also plan to add a few integrations: as mentioned above, a single Input_sentenceN with the possibility to add n phrases separated by a comma would be more suitable to the final user. Furthermore, the model could be even more effective if the user could give negative information, expliciting, for example, retrievals that are not desired.

Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic

Exploring Synonym Detection for Old Church Slavonic

We explored a variety of state-of-the-art embedding techniques and models aimed at finding semantic similarities among numerical word representations. Indeed, we are exploring the possibility of detecting synonyms by training models on Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic texts.

The aim is to understand widely used models, such as Word2Vec [11], Skip-Gram, and Continuous Bag of Words (CBOW) architectures, and their extensions, which include sub-word information in FastText [12]. We will go deep into the ability and capabilities of these techniques to handle ancient texts for which limited resources are available. Based on this, we are studying the strengths and limitations of each model to understand which performs better for the semantic similarity detection.

Enhancing the Development of a Morphological Analyzer for Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic texts

We are also exploring the development of morphological analyzers. In this sense, we are exploring the possibility of leveraging advanced NLP models like Slavic BERT [13], a pre-trained language model specifically fine-tuned for Slavic languages. Slavic BERT is part of the BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) [14] family, which uses a transformer-based architecture that excels in capturing both the syntactic and semantic relationships within a text by processing input bidirectionally. This facilitates it to understand the contextual meaning of words in a sentence, and the model can detect grammatical properties such as person, number, tense, mood, voice, gender, case, etc. Indeed, it is well known that the model's self-attention mechanism allows it to capture complex relationships between these features, enabling a more nuanced understanding of the language's structure efficiently.

Whilst Slavic BERT has shown good abilities in handling intricate morphological patterns and variations in Slavic languages like Polish, Czech, Ukrainian, and Russian, based on our preliminary experiments, the pre-trained model cannot handle Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic (in particular Old Church Slavonic). Thus, we aim at fine-tuning Slavic BERT on the available annotated dataset and measure the model's ability to predict grammar properties like person, number, tense, mood, voice, gender, case, etc.

Sanskrit

Introductory premise:

At present, in the existing databases of Sanskrit texts, the most complex operations related to the morphology of the Sanskrit language, such as the recognition and separation of phonetic phenomena called sandhi, lemmatization and morphosyntactic analysis have been done manually and only to a small extent automatically.

The objective pursued within the ITSERR project and specifically within Work Package 4 DaMSym (Data Mining: the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Symbolum) in its components working on the Sanskrit language was to take as a starting text a short work such as the Sanskrit translation of the Christian Creed in its Nicene-Constantinopolitan version and to collect a corpus of Sanskrit reference texts on which to make the comparison in order to obtain a machine learning model program for Sanskrit that allows these operations to be carried out using machine learning techniques in Python, the methodological approaches and results of which are described and explored below.

Workflow description:

Regarding the word embedding extraction, Igor Spanò worked closely with the IT component of the University of Palermo, composed of doctoral student Irfan Ali and Prof. Marco La Cascia. Once transcribed the translation of the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed into Sanskrit by Mill (1823), Igor Spanò proceeded to separate the sandhis, morphosyntactic analysis, and translation.

Fig. 32: Printed text of the Sanskrit translation of the Creed (1823).

The results of this work and the philological, historical-religious, and philosophical investigations concerning the Sanskrit Creed have resulted in a scholarly article by Igor Spanò, that has already been accepted for publication by the journal 'Studi e Materiali di Storia delle Religioni' entitled: Decoding the Divine. W.H. Mill's Sanskrit Rendition of the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed and Its Religious and Linguistic Resonance. The next phase of this work focused on the creation of a digitized model of the text of the Creed, both in its unseparated and separated sandhis versions, which was provided to Irfan Ali.

There are two main challenging concepts in the Sanskrit NLP processing language: Sandhi and Sandhi split. Sandhi refers to a phonetic transformation at word boundaries, where two or more words are combined to form a new word like the following one:

vidyA + AlayaH = vidyAlayaH (Vowel Sandhi)
vAk + hari = vAgGari (Consonant Sandhi)
punaH + api = punarapi (Visarga Sandhi)

Fig. 33: Example of Sanskrit Sandhi Words

Sandhi division, however, breaks down Sanskrit compounds and phonetically fused (sandhified) words into their individual morphemes, as shown below.

tadupAsanIyam = tat + upAsanIyam
tadupAsanIyam = tat + upa + AsanIyam

Fig. 34: Example of Sanskrit Sandhi Split Words

Sandhi Split of the Sanskrit Compound Word:

We focused on the sandhi split of the compound words of the Sanskrit text using neural networks and Python. This task involves the added complexity of not only accurately splitting the compound words but **also determining where to make the splits** because the Sanskrit language is inflectional and morphologically complex. Since a Sanskrit compound can be divided in several ways as shown in figure 34, resulting in different possible interpretations, some split words may be syntactically correct but lack semantic significance. Determining the semantic significance of the compound word is context dependent. An automatic sandhi division program will help facilitate the learning and teaching of the language,, which makes Sanskrit teacher - and student - friendly.

Fig. 35: Example of different possible split locations of the Sanskrit compound word māmabhiḡatāḡ

Methodology:

To solve the sandhi split of the compound word, we focused on predicting the position first where to split the compound word. For this problem, we designed deep-learning neural model-based bi-encoders and multi-head attention to predict the valid split location with the help of the sandhi window where the sandhi variation will take place in the Sanskrit compound word.

Predicting the location of the compound word can be seen as a sequence-to-sequence problem. The input sequence consists of the compound word and the target output sequence is an integer array with an equal number of elements as the characters in the compound word, where each location indicates whether a split occurs after that character like 1 for the split and 0 for no split. Our model

takes the sequence of the character of the compound word of the Sanskrit language. Our model consists of two Bi-LSTMs named forward and backward LSTMs that act as encoders to extract the character level contextual information of each input character. Multi-head attention is used to capture the short-term and long-term dependencies between the output of both Bi-LSTMs to predict the valid split position in the compound word. We consider the sandhi window of length 4 where the prediction of splitting the compound word would take place as given in the following figure 36.

Fig. 36: Example of Sandhi Window of Size 4 of the Sanskrit compound word

In the above example for the *tasmādāgamikam* compound word, you can see that the split prediction should be after the second element 'd' that takes a value of 1 in the output array.

Our model architecture consists of three main components:

1. A character Embedding layer.
2. Two Bi-LSTMs extract the contextual information from both forward and backward sequences.
3. A Multi-head Attention module to capture the short-term and long-term dependencies of the different parts of the sequence and extract the most relevant information to predict the valid split point.

The complete architecture of our designed model is shown in Figure 37 below.

Fig. 37: Architecture of the Sanskrit Compound Word Split Prediction Model

a. A character Embedding layer:

The characters of the input sequence which belong to the set of language symbols of size V are represented as a one-hot encoding strategy and then symbols are mapped in embedding space.

Given,

Input sequence: $X \in R^{T \times V}$, where T is the sequence length and V is the vocabulary size

Embedding Matrix: $E \in R^{V \times d}$, where d is the embedding dimension

The embedding operation can be written as:

$$E_x = XE, \quad \text{where } E_x \in R^{T \times d} \text{ is the embedding sequence} \quad (1)$$

b. Left and Right Context Bi-Encoders as bi-LSTMs:

We utilized two bi-directional LSTMs as encoders named left context and right context encoders to capture full contextual information from both ends of the sequence.

We call a first bi-LSTM as left context encoder that processes the input sequence in natural order and at each time t , it computes:

$$\text{Forward LSTM: } \vec{h}_t = LSTM_{fw}(x_t, \vec{h}_{t-1}) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Backward LSTM: } \overleftarrow{h}_t = LSTM_{bw}(x_t, \overleftarrow{h}_{t+1}) \quad (3)$$

The output for the left context (first bi-LSTM) would be the concatenation of forward and backward LSTM:

$$h_t^{left} = [\vec{h}_t, \overleftarrow{h}_t], \quad \text{where } h_t^{left} \in R^{2n} \text{ and } n \text{ is the number of cell units.} \quad (4)$$

The second bi-LSTM named right context encoder processes the input sequence x' in backward order and each time t , it computes:

$$\text{Forward LSTM (on the reversed sequence): } \vec{h}'_t = LSTM'_{fw}(x'_t, \vec{h}'_{t-1}) \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Backward LSTM (on the reversed sequence): } \overleftarrow{h}'_t = LSTM'_{bw}(x_t, \overleftarrow{h}'_{t+1}) \quad (6)$$

Similar to the first bi-LSTM, the output for the second bi-LSTM (right context) would be the concatenation of forward and backward LSTM:

$$h_t^{right} = [\vec{h}'_t, \overleftarrow{h}'_t], \quad \text{where } h_t^{right} \in R^{2n} \text{ and } n \text{ is the number of cell units.} \quad (7)$$

All the LSTMs used the Hyperbolic tangent activation function.

Using two Bi-directional LSTMs processing different contexts separately has advantages over a single Bi-LSTM with $2n$ units. In the dual context approach, the preceding-context Bi-LSTM would be able to capture dependencies starting from the beginning of a sequence to each point, and the following-context Bi-LSTM from each point to the end. This will lead to a nuanced understanding of the preceding and following contexts, which is important for making correct split location predictions within Sanskrit compound words. Additionally, using two Bi-LSTMs with fewer units each offers better regularization and generalization compared to a single Bi-LSTM with many units. Furthermore, independent regularization techniques, especially dropout, help minimize the risk of overfitting, which can hinder a model's ability to generalize to new, unseen data. This effectively balances the complexity associated with splitting Sanskrit compounds and enhances overall model performance.

c. Multi-Head Attention Layer:

Multi-head Attention is a module for attention mechanisms used in natural language processing tasks that runs through an attention mechanism several times in parallel. We utilized the multi-head

attention mechanisms to capture the short-term and long-term dependencies of the different parts of the sequence aiming to help in identifying the valid split point in the Sanskrit compound word. This attention mechanism converts the inputs into three vectors, Query, Key, and Value, and computes the attention as,

$$(Q, K, V) = \text{Softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (8)$$

In our model, the attention mechanism considers the output of two bi-LSTMs as;

$$Q = H^{left}, K = H^{right}, \text{ and } V = H^{right} \quad (9)$$

For identifying the valid split location, multiple attention heads are very important because this helps us extract the varying information from the data.

So, for the multi-headed attention with H heads,

$$\text{Muti - Head}(Q, K, V) = \text{Concat}(\text{head}_1, \text{head}_2, \dots, \text{head}_H) W^o \quad (10)$$

where $\text{head}_i = \text{Attention}(QW_i^Q, KW_i^K, VW_i^V)$ and W^o is the output weight matrix

So, for the multi-head attention, the output for our model would be,

$$A = \text{MultiHead}(H^{left}, H^{right}, H^{right}) \quad (11)$$

Target Sequence:

In the end, the output of the two bi-LSTMs and multi-head attentions would be concatenated to get the desired target sequence.

$$H^{merged} = \text{Concat}(H^{left}, A, H^{right}) \quad (12)$$

d. Dropout Layer:

One of the regularization techniques in neural networks that is mainly used to avoid overfitting problems is the dropout. To prevent overfitting while training the model, we used a dropout after each layer. It works by randomly dropping out a fraction of neurons during training. This prohibits any given model from relying on the strength of any given neuron or small sets of neurons, thus forcing the network to learn more general and robust features. This gives the model the ability to generalize better on unseen data, so in the end, this improves the performance on the validation and test sets. Every time a dropout layer is applied, it works as a different model with a smaller size, essentially simulating the benefit of training an ensemble of networks.

e. Normalization Layer:

Using the normalization layer after the dropout would improve the training process and model performance. Dropout introduces randomness since some neurons are disabled, which generally causes other active neurons' activations to fluctuate. A normalization layer would stabilize this kind of activations and make the training process more consistent. Moreover, normalization can speed up convergence by avoiding internal covariate shifts, so the model learns more efficiently and the distribution of inputs to each layer remains more consistent. Further, dropout combined with normalization might lead to a synergistic effect since normalization itself is a sort of regularization and thus provides better generalization on unseen data. This could help the model to be insensitive to the initial weights and make it performant in various initializations. Overall, a normalization layer after dropout provides more robustness to the model.

f. Dense Layer:

When capturing the global dependencies and local context after the concatenation of two bi-LSTMs and multi-head attention, it will be at the disposal to the dense layer with one neuron used to estimate the valid split window. The dense layer uses a sigmoid activation function.

g. Tools used for Sandhi Split:

We used Python with Keras API running on the TensorFlow backend. We also utilized the Sanscript tool that converts the International Alphabet of Sanskrit Transliteration (IAST) format of our dataset to Sanskrit Library Phonetic (SLP) format because it is a better scheme suitable for computational analysis to improve the performance of the model.

Arabic

Introductory premise

There are several language technology resources for Arabic that allow the development of modern systems for the study of large corpora in this language, ranging from State of the Art generative LLMs such as Jais¹, encoder LLMs such as CamelBERT² and several parsers and lemmatizers. Thanks to this flourishing environment, several applications developed for English can be replicated in Arabic. Certain challenges can be addressed through better infrastructure, such as larger storage units and

¹ <https://huggingface.co/inceptionai/jais-13b-chat>

² <https://huggingface.co/CAMEL-Lab/bert-base-arabic-camelbert-mix>

more efficient compute hardware, moreover, implementing fast similarity based searches over this corpus demands efficient embedding and querying technologies.

Fig. 38: The interface to a search engine exploring the OpenITI corpus.

Methodology

To access and explore the corpus proficiently, we developed a search engine that performs similarity searches across every available document, this means that a user can search for passages with content similar to the one they are looking for, e.g. one can search for occurrences of the word *Father* focusing on those instances where its meaning is closer to the one it has in the *Creed*.

To create a semantic representation space, which allows for similarity search, we use an Encoder Language Model trained on billions of tokens, a reproduction of BERT trained on Arabic corpora, *CAMEL-Lab/bert-base-arabic-camelbert-mix*, to extract **word embeddings** from all the texts in the corpus. After encoding all the tokens, we create an index for fast searches, we can thus perform fast similarity search, looking for the most similar passages within the corpus according to the language model semantic representation of text in numerical form (each word is assigned a vector of length 768, which represents the word meaning in the representation space create by the model during training).

In Figure 38, we show the interface to the search engine, which allows for a search over the OpenITI corpus by selecting 4 parameters: (1) **Word to search** (top left) the specific word to search; (2) **Year** (top right) a passage that encodes the contextual meaning of the word to perform more accurate matching (e.g. the possible meaning of *father* in different passages "someone's father" and "the Father" as mentioned in the *Credo*); (3) **Passage to embed the word** (middle left), a textual context to inform the meaning of the Word to search; (4) **Number of samples to show** (bottom left) a number of results to return from the search.

After entering the parameters, the engine returns the results in the form of a number (Number of samples to show) of text passages is retrieved, for each text passage the similarity with the original word is also reported and finally a link to the original document in the OpenITI corpus, where the matching passage is found (this is reported as the url to the document on the OpenITI github page^[2]). Performing fast searches over the full OpenITI corpus is compute, memory and storage demanding since the dataset contains approximately ~30 Gigabytes of data (for a comparison, Wikipedia is ~20 Gigabytes), to address this we use the FAISS library to index the full corpus and perform fast similarity searches, in particular, we instantiate a 4bit quantized index for each time range in the OpenITI corpus, e.g. 0250AH. Currently the search output helps in fast document understanding and it provides fast retrieval of original documents to easily identify content relevant to specific research questions across the whole OpenITI corpus.

4. Document understanding through comparison with corpora

Sanskrit

Within the text of the Sanskrit translation of the Creed, Igor Spanò proceeded to identify some significant semantic patterns, selecting certain terms and clusters of terms in the digitized text, in order to search for their occurrences within the Corpus and verify their semantic value, position and connections within individual verses or sentences. The direction in which this investigation was carried out aimed at identifying synonyms and antonyms concerning both single words and pairs of words, verifying that their meaning in the context of the reference Corpus works could be analogous to that of their use in Mill's Sanskrit translation and highlighting semantic relationships, which are often not immediately evident. The keywords and term pairs first identified and to be traced within the Corpus were as follows:

- 1) *tāta* father (referring to God)

in conjunction with the following words: *eka, sraṣṭr, mahātāta, deva, sarvabhūta, nisev, man-*

- 2) *putra* son (referring to Jesus)

in conjunction with the following words: *man-, nissṭa, sarvabhūta, nisev*

- 3) *puṇyātman* holy spirit

in conjunction with the following words: *īśa, jīvana, vara, tāta, putra, śrutakīrti, nisev, śakti*

Of these individual words or pairs of terms, Irfan Ali's investigations yielded the following results:

tāta padre/father
eka, sraṣṭr, mahātāta, deva, sarvabhūta, nisev, man
sraṣṭr
putra figlio/son
man, nissrta, sarvabhūta, nisev
nissrta
punyātman spirito santo/holy spirit
īśa, jivana, vara, tāta, putra, śrutakīrti, nisev, śakti

I am facing some issues regarding the words/lemmas:

I haven't found the exact word or lemma **mahātāta** in the dataset. (as per my understanding)

mahātāta
mahā - This prefix means "great," "large," "mighty," or "important."
tāta - This can mean "father," "dear one," or "beloved."
Together as **mahātāta**, it could potentially mean "great father," or "mighty dear one."

sarvabhūta
I have found the exact word **sarvabhūta** in the dataset. Only one word exists in the entire dataset as per my understanding.
The term **sarvabhūta** is a compound word in Sanskrit composed of:
sarva - This means "all" or "every."
bhūta - This means "being," "creature," or "entity."
When combined, **sarvabhūta** translates to "all beings" or "all creatures."

nissrta
I haven't found the exact word **nissrta** in the dataset. (as per my understanding)

nissrta - This term consists of:
nis - This prefix means "out," "forth," "away," or "without."
srta - Derived from the root **sr**, which means "to go," "to move," "to come forth," or "to emerge."
nissrta therefore denotes something that has emerged, come forth, or been extracted.

punyātman
punya - This Sanskrit word means "virtue," "goodness," "merit," or "righteousness."
ātman - This term means "soul," "self," or "spirit." In philosophical and spiritual contexts, it often refers to the individual self or the essence of a person.
When combined, **punyātman** can be interpreted as "one whose essence is virtuous," "a soul filled with goodness," or "a person characterized by righteousness."

But in the dataset, I found this word **punyātmanā**. (Only one word exists in the entire dataset as per my understanding.)

Word	Lemma
punya	punya
ātmanā	ātman

nisev
I haven't found the exact word or lemma **nisev** in the dataset. (as per my understanding)

Fig. 39: Preliminary results of the comparison with the corpus of terms and term pairs found in the Sanskrit version of the Creed

Considering the results established by Irfan Ali, it was decided to focus on finding occurrences within the reference corpus of the term *śrutakīrti*, used by Mill in the sense of 'prophet', and the following pairs of terms:

- 1) the term *tāta*, used by Mill in the context of the translation of the Creed exclusively in the meaning of 'father', in conjunction with the term *eka*, 'one';
- 2) the term *tāta* in conjunction with the term *deva*, used by Mill in the sense of 'God';
- 3) the term *tāta* in conjunction with the verbal root *man-*, used by Mill with the meaning of 'believe', in the sense of religious faith;
- 4) the term *putra*, used by Mill in the sense of 'Son [of God]', in conjunction with the verbal root *man-*

Searching these terms within the reference Corpus produced the following results:

- 1) The term *śrutakīrti* occurs 17 times
- 2) The term pair *tāta/eka* occurs 11 times
- 3) The term pair *tāta/deva* occurs 21 times

within the corpus, these terms appear is often referable to precise ritual scenarios or epic characters and events, or narrative spheres in a broad sense.

5) It can be seen, therefore, that within the corpus there are no precise cases of synonymy or antonymy for the terminological choices adopted by Mill in the translation of the Creed into Sanskrit.

6) Although not used by Mill within his translation of the Creed, the recurrence in many texts of the compound *devaputra*, 'son of god', often in the plural form (in Hindu as well in Buddhist texts), appears interesting and deserving of further investigation from a historical-religious point of view.

7) The semantic overlaps between the clusters of terms identified make it possible in some cases to verify or illuminate the translation strategies found in the Sanskrit Creed, although in most cases the 'Christian' meaning attributed to the terms is only detectable from the context of the translation of the Creed.

8) On the other hand, it is precisely the semantic differences found that provide stimuli for comparative investigations and the perspectives of historical-religious, philosophical and philological studies.

5. Properties visualization

Latin

Properties visualization is nowadays easily achievable via dedicated softwares. Once accomplished the encoding step, scholars have at their disposal vectors that can be exploited in many promising tasks. WP4 is particularly interested in calculating relations among word-embedded vectors and comparing them through periods and locations. Instead of considering terms as atoms, approaching words as vectors allows to calculate distances among them (cosine similarity techniques) and to identify trends in probability of co-occurrences. This approach finds its core idea in the same principle that John Rupert Firth summarized in 1957 that “you shall know a word by the company it keeps” and is here applied to the NC Symbol, case study of WP4, with the tools that digital humanities and computational linguistics offer nowadays. Federico Iezzi and Elia Scapini have taken confidence with visualization properties techniques, especially exploring tools and models offered by [Sketch engine](#), [Voiant](#) and the aforementioned TLG. Furthermore, testing the latin embedder realized last June with the tagged florilegium provided by Iezzi and Scapini, IT Team has also produced column graphs representing the probability confidence the model had that a certain word was synonymous with a target term from NC. Some initial results appear in the figure 40 below.

Fig. 40: Initial quality data retrieved from the model developed from IT Team

Ancient Greek

State of the art visualization tools are exploited in the [Agalma web page](#) (on Hugging Face) to show how Ancient Greek words are in relation with their context through time in a dynamic way. This project, based on a Word2Vec architecture was released at the end of May 2024 and is cured by Silvia Stopponi and her Team for the University of Groningen.

Wp4, in any case, is exploring not just the similarity between words through time, but also the sentence closeness in a corpus in a diachronic way. Therefore, we plan to adopt the most suited tools to describe sentence similarity, instead of word similarity. For example, the embedding process described at the third point of this deliverable that has led to similarity comparison can also be

visualized in a two-dimensional graph. To achieve this visualization goal we ask the software to reduce multi-dimensional vectors to two dimensions, for this step we exploited one of the most common techniques: t-SNE (t-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding). Reducing vectors to two dimensions allows one to spread and visualize them in a two-dimensional graph where the closer the words/sentences stand, the more they are similar according to the model. In the following example, the target phrase, “Φῶς ἐκ Φωτός, Θεὸν ἀληθινὸν ἐκ Θεοῦ ἀληθινοῦ” is preceded by a red dot to make it easier to find it, while phrases from the corpus are in blue.

Fig. 41: Visualization of sentences spreaded on a two-dimensional space according to their meaning

We plan to apply a few additional adjustments to the visualization of similarity in sentences. For example, we could fix the target phrase, Input_phraseN in the center of the graph and ask the model to spread all the other sentences around it, the closer, the more similar. We also consider broadening our visualization tools, especially including 3-dimensional visualization graphs that can be dynamically surfed by the interested scholars as shown in the figure below. The best case would be gaining the possibility to visualize in 3-dimensions the semantic surrounding of the target expressions through time in various colors.

Fig. 42: Visualization of sentences spreaded on a three-dimensional space according to their meaning

In the case of Middle Russian (14th-17th centuries) it is also possible to view the frequency index in the corpus and a cluster of similar words.

Fig. 44: Visualization of the term **богъ** in the Middle Russian Corpus

The ultimate goal of WP4’s work in the case of Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic texts is to apply this function to all words in the corpus (beyond periodization) and additionally to visualize grammatical relationships between the terms (when the researched term is “subject of”; “a modifier”; “Prec prep”; “gen modifier”; “and – that is the list of word to which is more often associated”). Below is an example of the research’s results of the term сын (son) on Sketch Engine (the available corpus is in modern Russian).

Fig. 45: Visualization of the the term **сын** on Sketch Engine

Thus in terms of visualization the aim we would like to reach is:

- To visualize the grammatical properties and the semantic cluster of the researched term (beyond periodization).
- To visualize its grammatical features and the list of terms to which it is most frequently associated with.

Sanskrit

As mentioned earlier, the visualization of properties already present in several works in the Digital Corpus of Sanskrit was used for the purposes of the moment. The tagging system was carried out manually (and only to a small extent, relating to morphosyntactic analysis, by computer programs), and makes it possible to display, by clicking on the individual lexical units of a text, a textual interface containing the morpho-tactical analysis of the word and its meaning in English, taken from the most common Sanskrit dictionaries, as well as to search for the presence and position of the word in the other texts in the Corpus itself. Large parts of the annotations are available for download.

Texts

[Help](#)

Select a text:

Select a chapter:

BAU 1.1 (no revisions)

Associated topic(s): [sacrificial_horse](#)

Show parallels Show headlines
Use dependency labeler
Chapter id: 9100

- Click on a sentence to show its analysis
- Keep the mouse pointer over a lemma to show its meanings.

uṣā vā aśvasya medhyasya śiraḥ / (1.1) [Par.?](#)

sūryas cakṣus vātaḥ prāṇo vyāttaṃ agniḥ vaiśvānaraḥ saṃvatsara
ātmāśvasya medhyasya / (1.2) [Par.?](#)

dyauḥ pṛṣṭham antarikṣam udaram pṛthivi pājasyam dīśaḥ pārśve
avāntaradīśaḥ pārśava ṛtavo 'ṅāni māśās cārḍhamāśās ca parvāny
ahorātrāṇi pratīṣṭhā nakṣatrāṇy asthīni nabho māṃsāni / (1.3) [Par.?](#)

ūvadhyaṃ sīkatāḥ sindhavo guḍā yakṛcca klomāś ca parvatā oṣadhayaś
ca vanaspatayaś ca lomāni / (1.4) [Par.?](#)

Fig. 46: Example of properties visualization in the Digital Corpus of Sanskrit

Finally, based on historical principles, the Digital Corpus of Sanskrit makes it possible to display a statistical evaluation of word presence within texts. This model could be the basis for training the machine learning model on the ability to provide lexical-linguistic and morphosyntactic annotation of terms within texts.

6. Objectives and further projects

Latin

Accomplished Objectives

We have selected and incorporated Corpus Corporum as the primary data source. This decision was based on its comprehensive meta-data, including periods and authors, making it suitable for the objectives of WP₄ projects. The initial intention to incorporate data from 100CC was discarded due to the quality issues such as missing meta-data and the inclusion of irrelevant material like “lorem ipsum” text. As a result, Corpus Corporum was preferred for its cleanliness and structure.

Additionally, WP₄ has explored testing and evaluating Part-of-Speech (PoS) tagging tools, ultimately considering that, by an initial impression, the Lindat tool outperforms others tested, including WebLithc, ANNIS, and Morpheus. This choice will support future text analysis within the project.

The team has also advanced in developing Latin language embedding techniques, acknowledging the challenges posed by the inflected nature of Latin and Ancient Greek. An exchange with Alek Keersmaekers, a Digital Humanist, has been initiated to explore how to incorporate morphological and syntactical information into the embedding process.

Finally, WP₄ has also experimented with existing Latin encoders, presenting qualitative results in June 2024. These tests, focused on the semantic analysis of terms related to the Trinity, were carried out using a selection of fragments annotated by Federico Iezzi and Elia Scapini.

Further steps

Efforts to refine Latin WordNet synsets for the terms “Pater” “Filius” and “Spiritus” are ongoing. The synsets currently available contain inaccuracies that need to be addressed, such as the inclusion of irrelevant terms like “genitor” and “parens” for “Pater”. A more focused set of synsets is being developed to better align with the theological context of the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed. The team plans to complement this work by comparing the Latin synsets with resources from CoPhiWordNet, aiming to resolve existing deficiencies. Finally we are also considering exploring Latin BERT models and sBERT models for semantic retrieval tasks.

Ancient Greek

Accomplished Objectives

Significant progress has been made in the project thus far. A small test corpus has been successfully created from the works of Eustathius of Antioch, allowing for the initial stages of testing BERT models (Ancient Greek, Logion). Exploratory tests using retrieval software were conducted on this corpus, providing insights into its functionality and performance. As a result, improvements were made to the software, optimizing it for future use.

Further steps

The collection of all fragments attributed to Eustathius is still underway, with substantial progress already achieved. However, the process is ongoing to ensure completeness. Additionally, efforts to apply PoS tagging to the Eustathian corpus have started, but the task is yet to be fully completed, especially when it comes to integrating PoS information into the encoded vectors. We plan to set quality benchmarks using also SHLM-grc-en.

Pre modern Slavic

Accomplished Objectives

The work done so far has been devoted to collecting texts from the different corpora available online and to the searching of collaborative possibilities in order to supplement it. Possibilities for collaboration have been explored with the *National Russian Language Corpus* (mentioned above) team, with the Italian Prin on Maximus the Greek at the University of Pisa (*Italia umanistica e Moscovia cinquecentesca: digitalizzazione e mappatura digitale dell'opera di Massimo il Greco - PRIN 2022 PNRR*). Further possibilities of collaboration have been explored with the research team of the University of Freiburg on the front of corpus expansion using OCR and HTR techniques.

Tests were also conducted in order to be able to proceed with lemmatization of terms. As mentioned above, these tests gave good results, and first attempts of research were conducted in order to obtain the synonym detection applying the word2vec model on the corpus by attempting CBOW usage techniques and skip-gram techniques and checking the results for synonymous relationships between terms. In addition it has implemented the FastText model on the same corpus to compare its results with those obtained with the application of Word2Vec. Finally, has been conducted a comparison of the results of 1) Word2Vec in skip-gram mode and 2) CBOW and 3) with the results of FastText. In both cases the results returned the word declension and that is why it was decided to define synsets of some terms that were defined from an analysis of the results returned by *Ruscorpora* and *Sketch Engine* so as to refine the model. At the same time, morphosyntactic analysis is being integrated using existing tools such as *Stanza*, *Slavic Bert* and *Weblicht*.

Further steps

The next steps of the work with regard to the case study of Old Church Slavonic (OCS) and Church Slavonic will involve:

- the systematization of the dataset;
- the improvement of the techniques for synonymy research by unifying the research methodologies, as far as possible, with those of the other case studies covered by the WP;
- a clearer definition of visualization properties thanks to the activities carried out in cooperation with the *Unguess* team for the elaboration of user stories and user requirements;
- the analysis of the feasibility of integrating lemmatization and morphosyntactic annotation into the search results of individual terms will be explored.

Sanskrit

Accomplished Objectives

Igor Spanò and Irfan Ali developed a reference corpus of Sanskrit texts using digital repositories like the Digital Corpus of Sanskrit (DCS). They focused on creating a lemmatized dataset and training machine learning models tailored to Sanskrit's unique linguistic complexities. Key tasks included automating compound word (sandhi) splitting and lemmatization, enhancing the corpus for in-depth

research. Given Sanskrit's rich inflectional system and limited annotated datasets, the team applied advanced techniques such as Python-based tokenization. Their work involved analyzing the Sanskrit translation of the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed to uncover semantic patterns and compare these with reference texts, revealing meaningful semantic shifts that merit further historical-religious study. Irafan Ali implemented a neural network-based sandhi-splitting model, which supports compound word separation, essential for accurate Sanskrit text analysis. This model is designed to improve philological precision in processing ancient texts. The DCS was useful for visualizing morphological structures, providing a base for statistical analysis and future NLP model enhancements. These achievements lay the groundwork for more sophisticated computational tools in Sanskrit linguistics.

Further steps

In the coming months, the work will continue in the direction already taken, i.e. to continue training the machine learning model for Sanskrit, improving its accuracy. In particular, the automatic and reliable management of morphosyntactic analysis, and thus the unraveling of *sandhi*, will make it possible to proceed with the lemmatization of other Sanskrit texts and expand the reference corpus. Furthermore, since due to the effect of *sandhi*, a Sanskrit compound can be split in several ways, resulting in several possible interpretations, we hope to reach the level of semantic analysis as well, since determining the meaning of words often depends on the context.

Arabic

Accomplished Objectives

We have acquired some manuscript sources according to an accurate database that reports all the witnesses identified. These codices constitute the starting point of the research, since there are no digital editions of the Creed available. Furthermore, we have chosen *Kitab* as the main corpus, taking into account that there are no digital corpora of Arab-Christian tradition. *Kitab* is the Arabic subcorpus of the Open Islamicate Texts Initiative (Open ITI), which was founded in 2016 by M. Romanov, S. Savant and M. Miller as a multi-institutional effort to create not only a scientifically curated and open corpus of Islamicate (mainly Arabic and Persian) texts compliant with international data standards, accompanied by scholars metadata and representative of the diversity of historic traditions, but also a full digital text production pipeline. To date, *Kitab* corpus comprises more than 10,200 text files plus their corresponding metadata. Most of them contain pre-modern works from its origins in the second century AH up to roughly the ninth century AH. The works come from a variety of sources that fall within three major categories: 1. digital online libraries such as al-Maktaba al-Shamila and Shia Online; 2. research projects such as the Graeco-Arabic Studies Corpus; 3. OCR-pipeline based on Kraken. Moreover, through the creation of an interface to a search engine it will be possible to explore the corpus Open ITI and identify some words of Creed within it.

Further steps

Through the use of the search engine created by CNR, the identification of the terms/vectors within the corpus is in progress, with the aim of determining a possible synonymy/antonymy with the words of Creed. Future steps include a careful study focused on optimizing and customizing the tool with potential extensions for non-native Arabic speakers; we will test the possibility of introducing machine translation technologies to translate the English summaries for a wider audience.

Outline of Deliverable 4.1.2

In conclusion, we briefly outline how we envision the next whitepaper dedicated to the description of Deliverable 4.1.2. that will be focused on the *results gained using DaMSym on Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed*.

Deliverable 4.1.2 runs as follows:

This whitepaper illustrates the perspectives of scientific advancement that can be achieved thanks to the future platform DaMSym, drawing from the experience of the scholar community dealing with similar research issues. It presents the results of its operation "on the field", describing both the scientific results and the properties database obtained by operating DaMSym tools on the collected corpora in the different languages. As such, this deliverable not only validates DaMSym's prototypes, but also provides researchers with new material for their studies (still considering that the project is ongoing and that further testing and studies will come along till the end of the project by October 2025).

Along with the present whitepaper on Deliverable 4.1.1, we intend this next document as a report that both depicts the results that we currently own and both drafts perspectives of scientific advancement. Since it will be focused on the description of the future platform DaMSym, the next whitepaper will treasure the core gains that derive from the exchange we are currently entertained with the UNGUESS team and, therefore, will describe in detail the platform as it should become thanks to the User Stories workflow that we're now carrying on. Before detailing how DaMSym will be developed, shaped, allocated and maintained, we'll have to account for why we need it, meaning that a detailed state-of-the-art review of what is currently accessible to the scholarly community in terms of softwares for NLP of Ancient Languages such as are those we treat will be necessary. Further on, Deliverable 4.1.2 requires to describe results of the operation "on the field": on this point, we consider gathering a certain number of colleagues to test our prototypes and to administer a survey to understand how the "public" might perceive what we've made till now. Finally, in the last part of Deliverable 4.1.2, we discuss how we plan to transform the feedback received from the surveys into a number of improvement adjustments.

In sum, we are drafting a document with the following shape:

- Document overview
- State of the art for NLP tools and how DaMSym covers some gaps
- DaMSym platform prototypes general description (User Stories workflow)
- Survey: description and administration
- Perspectives of scientific advancement from the discussion of the surveys

- Conclusion
- Bibliography

7. Essential References

Latin and Ancient Greek

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